

ETHNIC DIALECTS IN AMERICAN ENGLISH AND THEIR
LINGUISTIC RELATIONS

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Abstract: this article focuses on language as a social phenomenon that is well-recognized to occur naturally and unavoidably in all human communities. As a result, the primary goal of linguistic research is to investigate the phonologies, grammatical structures, and semantics of various languages in order to shed light on how these languages are used in various social contexts. Many linguists think that although people are born with the ability to learn languages, they do not always use them since they are social beings who need interaction with others to become aware of their potential.

Аннотация: Эта статья посвящена языку как социальному явлению, которое, как известно, естественно и неизбежно возникает во всех человеческих сообществах. В результате основной целью лингвистических исследований является изучение фонологии, грамматических структур и семантики различных языков, чтобы пролить свет на то, как эти языки используются в различных социальных контекстах. Многие лингвисты считают, что, хотя люди рождаются со способностью к изучению языков, они не всегда используют их, поскольку они социальные существа, которым необходимо взаимодействие с другими людьми, чтобы осознать свой потенциал.

Xulosa: Ushbu maqola tilga barcha insoniyat jamoalarida tabiiy va muqarrar ravishda sodir bo'lishi yaxshi tan olingan ijtimoiy hodisa sifatida qaratilgan. Natijada, lingvistik tadqiqotlarning asosiy maqsadi bu tillarning turli xil ijtimoiy

sharoitlarda qanday ishlatilishini yoritib berish uchun turli tillarning fonologiyalari, grammatik tuzilmalari va semantikasini o'rganishdir. Ko'pgina tilshunoslarning fikriga ko'ra, odamlar tillarni o'rganish qobiliyatiga ega bo'lishsa-da, ular har doim ham ulardan foydalanmaydilar, chunki ular o'zlarining potentsiallaridan xabardor bo'lish uchun boshqalar bilan o'zaro munosabatlarga muhtoj bo'lgan ijtimoiy mavjudotlardir.

Keywords: language, society, dialect, artificial language, ethics.

Language is a social phenomenon that organically and inexorably develops in all human communities, as is well known. Therefore, the primary goal of linguistic research is to investigate the phonologies, grammatical structures, and semantics of the world's languages in order to shed light on how these languages work in various social contexts. Many linguists think that although people are born with the ability to acquire languages, they do not fully develop it until they interact with others in social situations. If we accept the notion advanced by linguists that language is a tool for communication, we must acknowledge that language is a system of signs that is used to convey information, both factual and non-factual (subjective, implicit, and creative).

Additionally, a variety of social, cultural, and regional quirks that are part of the language system are revealed through language use, namely speech. Because there is so much individualized, subjective information in natural languages, some scientists resolved to develop artificial languages that would solely express factual information and be devoid of expression. These languages were designed for human beings whose speech cannot be free of subjective judgment, which is why these attempts have so far failed. Undoubtedly, the network of electronic gear could benefit from the usage of artificial languages. When it comes to human communication, language cannot function as a rigid system. Speech exhibits a wide range of manifestations since it is utilized by various people and for various reasons. Dialect is one of the different linguistic subtypes. According to P.

Matheus, a dialect is any different variation of a language, particularly one that is spoken in a particular portion within a nation or other geographical location. The idea is that mutual ability should serve as the criterion for separating dialects from languages. Languages that are understood as a specific set of speech rules of a community are also a component of that community's greater culture. Language is a tool used by people to identify themselves with one cultural group and to distinguish themselves from others. Like other common behaviors, language usage within a community contributes to its culture and serves as a means of expressing group identity. Speaking styles serve as a tool for communication as well as a social status indicator for the speaker. Language variations are what linguists refer to as distinct ways of speaking, and this term includes dialects that are geographically or social culturally defined as well as the jargons or styles of subcultures. E. Finegan categorizes dialects into regional, ethnic, gender, and socioeconomic varieties of English and classifies them as linguistic variants (1:1999). We will concentrate on this national variety of English since the current study discusses the ethnic dialects of American English.

The following regional dialects are the most prevalent in North American English:

South or North. E. Finegan characterizes dialects as distinct linguistic variants. various English variations that reflect regional, ethnic, gender, and socioeconomic status (1:1999). Given that this essay is on the ethnic dialects of Americans. We will concentrate on this regional variant of English. The following regional dialects of North American English are most noticeable: Southern or New England, or Appalachian, Ozark, Minnesotan, or Texas. Regional dialects serve to identify the speaker's home region. Local dialects are in addition to regional dialects. A regional dialect is divided into local dialects. This may be specific to a particular city, such as New York, Pittsburg, or Boston, or even to particular

neighborhood of a city, such as between Brooklyn and the Bronx in New York City, or Beacon Hill and the South Side or back Bay in Boston.

It is assumed that mobility and education may diminish the distinctiveness of a regional dialect, but can seldom completely eradicate it. Social dialect or sociolect reveals the educational or class status of the speaker. In the United States, social dialect is more often associated with the stereotype of different national or local regions, ethnic groups, or educational levels than with - classes. A social dialect or sociolect is often revealed through language which indicates the cultural attitude and status preferences of the communities. These examples could include an individual's use of -politically-correct language, or the attitudes and perspectives revealed by the humor or social jargons one may use. Speaking the -wrong social dialect in a certain environment may result in awkwardness or difficulty for the speaker. For example, speaking a highly-educated dialect while working in a blue-collar environment would identify one as an - outsider who might become the subject of resentment or open hostility. If a black person speaks -standard English in a Black- Vernacular-English community, he could be regarded as a -traitor to his heritage. If a traveling sales professional speaks local or regional dialect which is perceived by others as having lower humorous status, he may be not regarded as authoritative or believable, and sales would not be made. Human language also varies in gender which is called gender dialect. Admittedly, the speech of males and females differs in more respects than just the pitch. That is why at present two gender dialects are acknowledged: male speech and female speech. Differences in male and female speech can also be found in vocabulary, grammar and phonology, as well as style, register and often even choice of topic and length and frequency of speech. To some extent, emerging -gay speech or - lesbian speech may be regarded as a subset of gender dialect. The next type of language variation which manifests itself in the form of dialect is the so-called ethnic dialect. If one belongs to an ethnic community, he/she may express

his/her membership in that community by speaking the ethnic dialect of that group. If we belong to an ethnic community, we may express our membership in that community by speaking the ethnic dialect of that group. So far, two ethnic dialects have been acknowledged in North American English: African American Vernacular English (formerly called Black English or Ebonics), which is spoken by black Americans, and Chicano English, which is spoken by Americans of Mexican descent. In order to understand the diversities which separate these language varieties and the similarities which unite them, it is necessary to examine the process of creation of these dialects which is undoubtedly connected with certain extralinguistic (historical) as well as linguistic (communicative needs) factors. As it has already been mentioned above, the next ethnic dialect of American English is Chicano English. Chicano English is a non-standard variety of English, influenced by contact with Spanish, and spoken as a native dialect by both bilingual and monolingual speakers. In addition, it is a variety of English that is obviously influenced by Spanish and that has low prestige in most circles, but that nevertheless is independent of Spanish and is the first, and often only, language of many hundreds of thousands of residents of California. According to Santa Ana, Chicano English is an ethnic dialect that children acquire as they acquire English in the barrios or other ethnic social setting during their language acquisition period. Necessarily, Chicano English is to be distinguished from the English of second language learners. As a matter of fact, Mexicans who make their first steps in English and those mastering English retain a peculiar accent which reveals their national background. Thus, Chicano English is spoken only by English speakers of Mexican descent. language acquisition period. Necessarily, Chicano English is to be distinguished from the English of second language learners. As a matter of fact, Mexicans who make their first steps in English and those mastering English retain a peculiar accent which reveals their national background. Thus, Chicano English is spoken only by English speakers of Mexican descent. In theory, one could use

the label - Chicano English to encompass any dialect spoken by people of Mexican origin in the USA, including both varieties that are identical to those of Anglos in the area, and varieties spoken by adult immigrants for whom English is a second language. Nonetheless, some of the studies of Chicano English published in the early 1980's seem to have misplaced elements of Metcalf's early definition. For example, Penfield and Ornstein-Galicia describe Chicano English as -a variety or dialect of English spoken predominantly by bilingual Chicanos... though they provide no evidence that bilinguals are more likely to speak Chicano English than monolinguals. Several of the early works also include discussion of whether Chicano English is actually a dialect of English separate from simply the non-native English of second language learners, often concluding that the answer is not yet known. In addition, Chicano English, in Sawyer's view, is merely a transitional stage or "stage in the acquisition of English" that a natural Spanish speaker must eventually pass through in order to speak a more "proper" version of English. Contrary to Sawyer, some academics like Metcalf, Bills, and Penalosa talk about Chicano English in terms of its link to Spanish, albeit they also differentiate it from Spanish on the way to a definition that treats it as a distinct dialect of English. Joyce Penfield and Jacob Ornstein-Galicia refer to Chicano English as "an ethnic, border dialect" in their book "Chicano English: An Ethnic Contact Dialect," which examines the Southwest as a sociolinguistic setting where language contact between Spanish and English variants plays a significant role. As such, much like any other regional or social variety, African American Vernacular English (AAVE) and Chicano English (CE) are legitimate varieties of American English. Both have complete grammatical structures that greatly resemble those of other English dialects. As such, much like any other regional or social variety, African American Vernacular English (AAVE) and Chicano English (CE) are legitimate varieties of American English. Both have complete grammatical structures that greatly resemble those of other English dialects.

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